

What is being a teacher in the countryside? Conceptions of Brazilian peasant higher education students about the Supervised Curricular Internship

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ABSTRACT. The present paper has the objective of analyzing students' conceptions about the supervised curricular internship in the Licentiate degree in Rural Education with qualification in Arts and Music, at the Federal University of Tocantins, Campus Tocantinópolis, Brazil. We also propose with this text to address the historical and pedagogical aspects of this course, as well as to discuss the importance of the Internship for the educators' training of to work in countryside schools. This case study was based on the qualitative approach, with documentary research and semi structured interviews with students of this course as data collection instruments. The type of data analysis - theoretical and empirical - followed the perspective of the interpretative research technique. The results demonstrated that in order to overcome the challenges faced by students and teachers of the Licentiate degree in Rural Education with qualification in Arts and Music of UFT in Tocantinópolis, demands elaborating a proposal of joint training between the training institutions and the school, in the sense to guarantee actions that will attend the various subjects, especially those of the Rural Education.

Keywords: supervised internship; degree in rural education; teacher training; higher education.

O que é ser professor do campo? Concepções de estudantes camponeses brasileiros de ensino superior acerca da realização do Estágio Curricular Supervisionado

RESUMO. O presente trabalho tem como objetivo analisar as concepções de estudantes acerca da realização do estágio curricular supervisionado no Curso de Licenciatura em Educação do Campo com habilitação em Artes e Música, na Universidade Federal do Tocantins, campus Tocantinópolis, Brasil. Ensejamos também com este texto abordar aspectos históricos e pedagógicos do referido curso, bem como discutir também a importância do Estágio para a formação de educadores e educadoras para a atuação em escolas localizadas no campo. Este estudo de caso se baseou na abordagem qualitativa, tendo como instrumentos de coletas de dados a pesquisa documental e entrevistas semiestruturadas com discentes do referido curso, além da pesquisa empírica. A forma de análise dos dados seguiu a perspectiva da técnica da pesquisa interpretativa. Os resultados demonstraram que para superação dos desafios enfrentados pelos estudantes e professores do curso de Licenciatura em Educação do Campo com habilitação em Artes e Música da UFT em Tocantinópolis, demanda a elaboração de uma proposta de estágio conjunta entre as instituições formadoras e a escola no sentido de garantir ações que venham atender os diversos sujeitos, principalmente os da Educação do Campo.

Palavras-chave: estágio curricular supervisionado; licenciatura em educação do campo; formação de professores; ensino superior.

Introduction

Rural education is a concept under construction which emerged in the 1990s in Brazil. It concerns an educational movement organized by rural workers and social movements that strive for a quality education that meets the peasant population reality, as well as their learning and knowledge needs (Caldart, 2012). The peasant population is extensive and diversified, characterized by family farmers,

riverine, quilombolas, extractivists, artisanal fishermen, settlers of the agrarian reform, indigenous people, caçaras, among others who produce their material conditions of existence through work in rural areas (Brasil, 2010).

The Licentiate degree in Rural Education¹ is an achievement of the struggles of social movements

¹ With respect to the curriculum of the degrees in Rural Education in Brazil, Hage, Molina, Silva, and Anjos (2018) emphasize that it presents a multidisciplinary

seeking for an education that meets the needs and specificities of the people living in and out of the countryside. Thus, the course works through the proposal of the Pedagogy of Alternation, that is, the teaching and learning processes occur in different spaces called University Time - TU, when the student is at the university studying the course subjects, and Community Time - TC, when the student is in his home community developing the works and research proposed by the teachers during the TU.

A crucial point of the degree in Rural Education with qualification in Arts and Music concerns the Supervised Internship, which is a new experience for teachers and students, given the dynamism of the course and for being the first group, considering that it began in 2014. The internship is understood as the articulating axis of the knowledge production in the whole development process of the course curriculum, which is based on the methodological principle that professional skills imply putting into practice the acquired sabers, both in academic life and in professional and personal life. In this sense, Piconez (2012, p. 14) points out that the “[...] relational context between practice-theory-practice presents important meaning in the formation of the teacher, since it guides the transformation towards the formation of the concept of unity”. Therefore, they are indissociable elements in the teaching profession.

In these aspects, Pimenta (2009) mentions that placements in undergraduate courses allow future educators to understand the complexity of institutional practices, as well as the actions practiced by professionals, which are necessary means for professional insertion.

Before these reflections, it is perceived that the internship is also understood as the articulating axis of the knowledge production throughout the course curriculum development process, based on the methodological principle that “[...] the development of professional competences implies putting the knowledge acquired, both in academic life and in professional and personal life” (Pimenta, 2009, p. 34). In this perspective, the author states that one often gets to know that the internship has a theoretical-practical role, that is, the theory is inseparable from the practice. Above all, this conception of the internship should be based on a look at what theory and practice mean in this context of teacher training. Based on this

understanding, it is possible to think of it in an investigative perspective of aspects related to the school routine of the students, teachers and society.

Based on this understanding and although some courses of teacher training do not establish a closer relation of the contents of the disciplines with the various school realities, one can not confuse and treat theory and practice as fragmented elements, but rather consider them in the process of teaching and learning in a contextualized way in pedagogical tasks, in order to understand the need to acquire theoretical knowledge to support pedagogical practice.

Although the Federal University of Tocantins (UFT) meets the Guidelines n. 11.788 of September 25 (Brasil, 2008), which provide for the students' internship, was proposed and elaborated by the teachers of the Rural Education course in Tocantinópolis campus, the internship guidelines for this course (*Universidade Federal do Tocantins [UFT], 2016*) since 2008 did not take into account the needs and specificities of the countryside subjects and this manual does not have elements contemplating the particularities of the course, especially in the specific areas: Arts and Music, and this in a way requires and refers to a more accurate look towards the completion of the internship.

Therefore, in order to elaborate such proposal, the conception of rural education was observed according to the scientific literature of the area, the subjects (students of the course) and the locality of the educational institutions. The starting point was the legal basis indicated by the Internship Act n. 11.788/2008 and the resolutions of the National Council of Education n. 1/2002 and n. 2/2002. It is worth mentioning that the Supervised Curricular Internship is developed from the fifth period in the UFT/Tocantinópolis Rural Education Course with a total workload of 405 (four hundred and five) hours.

One of the highlights of the Internship Guidelines is that the Supervised Internship can be carried out in schools with an urban area, providing that the group to be observed or to be held by the trainee meets at least 1/3 of students residing in the countryside, because the countryside schools located are not sufficient to meet the demand of students of the course. Regarding this characteristic, many questions were raised by students of the course and by the teachers in order to understand if the urban schools would have a proportion of students from the countryside; how to carry out internships in schools in the city; if the course is intended for the training of educators and rural educators, among others. After a diagnosis made by the teachers of the course, it was verified that the urban schools nearby

aspect, having as axis four areas of knowledge: a) arts, literature and languages; b) human and social sciences; c) natural sciences and mathematics; d) agricultural sciences.

the Tocantinópolis campus serve well more than 1/3 of countryside students.

In this sense, the objective of this article is to analyze the conception of peasant students about Supervised Curricular Internship in the Rural Education course at UFT/Tocantinópolis, seeking to understand the students' challenges and perspectives with regards to the accomplishment of the internship throughout the course. It is important to emphasize that this study is justified due to the fact that this subject is still little studied in the educational research, especially in what concerns the rural education. In fact, it is necessary to socialize this study to the academic community, in order to disseminate and contribute in the research expansion on the supervised curriculum internship in the training of teachers for the countryside.

Thus, for the development of this work, we used the qualitative approach research, which is characterized as a case study, following the perspective of the technique of interpretive research (Erickson, 1985), besides the documentary analysis of the Pedagogical Project of the Course (*Universidade Federal do Tocantins [UFT]*, 2013), part which deals with the Supervised Internship in Rural Education, as well as the analysis of teachers and students' experiences during the completion of Supervised Curricular Internship in the Rural Education course, with a degree in Arts and Music at the Federal University of Tocantins, Campus of Tocantinópolis, Brazil. With respect to the documentary analysis, "[...] it is another type of descriptive study that provides the investigator with the possibility of gathering a great deal of information about state education laws, school processes and conditions, study plans, etc". (Triviños, 1987, p. 111).

On the organization of this text, the first topic discusses a brief historical and pedagogical panorama of the degree in Rural Education in Brazil and in Tocantins, in order to contextualize the object of study. Next, the methodological procedures of the research and, in sequence, the data collected and analyzed in this study are presented. In the final part, the conclusions of this study are presented.

The degree in rural education in Brazil and in Tocantins: historical and pedagogical aspects

The current structure of Rural Education in Brazilian higher education institutions is the result of a process of struggle and conquest of several movements and segments of society, especially those linked to the countryside. Thus, the education of and in the countryside, understood as an education directed to people who live and depend on the

countryside, only began to be thought as the intensification of the class struggle that occurred in the 1990s (Aires, 2015).

If the Rural Education movement understands that the countryside school must be an ally of the social subjects in struggle to be able to exist as peasants; to continue the guarantee of the material reproduction of their rural work lives, it is imperative that the formation of educators who are being prepared to work in these schools should first of all consider that the existence and permanence (both of the schools and the subjects) necessarily passes through the paths that will be followed from the unfolding of the class struggle; from the result of the forces in dispute in the construction of the different field projects in Brazilian society (Molina, 2015, p. 146).

From this perspective, the Ministry of Education in Brazil (MEC) has developed a series of educational actions aimed at the rural population, among them the Program for Support to Higher Education in Undergraduate Rural Education (Procampo), which offers undergraduate in the final years of elementary and high school.

The first degree courses in Rural Education (Ledoc) started to be implemented in Brazil in 2006, through a pilot project developed in four Brazilian federal universities (Federal University of Minas Gerais, Federal University of Brasília, Federal University of Bahia and Federal University of Sergipe), which met the proposal formulated by the Ministry of Education, through the Department of Higher Education (SESu) and the Secretariat for Continuing Education, Literacy, Diversity and Inclusion (Secadi). These early experiences at these universities were essential to the expansion of higher education into the countryside.

According to Molina (2015), there are 42 public higher education institutions in Brazil that offer a degree in Rural Education with different qualifications, such as Sciences of Nature and Arts and Music, the latter being the only one in Latin America. It is worth noting that this expansion occurred through the struggles of social movements, in view of the fact that the funds of the states maintaining these graduations is also an essential factor for their functioning, since the offer of these courses are materialized by the proposal of Pedagogy of Alternation, which requires logistic and financial resources to meet the needs of people living in and out of the countryside.

Undergraduate degrees in Rural Education need to intensify and encourage dialogue and collective participation among teachers, since teacher training is complex and requires interactions between knowledge and acquirement in a participatory way

with rural communities, and as soon as possible, these relationships are carried out within each Higher Education Institute, the consolidation and identity formation of this new undergraduate degree will be better (Faleiro & Farias, 2016, p. 105).

Thus, the Program for Support to Higher Education in Undergraduate Rural Education (Procampo) through the Call for Proposals n. 02/2012 Sesu/Setec/Secadi/MEC/2012, continued with the extension of the Rural Degree courses in Brazil. With this expansion, the State of Tocantins was awarded two Undergraduate courses in Rural Education with qualification in Arts and Music, at the Federal University of Tocantins, Arraias and Tocantinópolis campus, these being the first qualification courses in Latin America. The main objective of this course is to train professionals to work in the final grades of Elementary and Secondary Education, and it lasts for four years, offered through the Pedagogy of Alternation, in which the teaching and learning process takes place in the University Time - when the students are in university studying the subjects of the course - and the Community Time, when the students return to the communities where they live, and develop the activities and research proposed by the teachers during the TU. This methodology is necessary throughout the course, as it is a way to enable the peasant student to remain in the countryside, without having to move to the city to attend the course (Faleiro & Farias, 2016).

After the first classes of the course in the state of Tocantins, Brazil, discussions and debates through meetings, seminars, and international congresses strengthened the process of insertion of Rural Education into the regional and state political agenda, making it possible to review the reality of the subjects in this context, aiming to fulfill the universal, human and social right to education, offering and guaranteeing means for the construction of a quality education that meets these human and social needs.

According to data from IBGE/2010, there are 29,852,986 people living in the countryside, which represents 15.65% of the population. In Tocantins, 293,212 thousand, or 21.19% of the population, a percentage higher than the national average, which is 15.65%. Regarding schooling, while in urban areas, the population aged 15 years or more has an average schooling of 7.3 years, in rural areas this average corresponds to 4 years (Gomes, Vizolli, Santos, & Stephani, 2017, p. 374).

With regard to the pedagogical aspects, in order to meet the demand of the rural people, the degree in Rural Education is offered through the proposal

of the Pedagogy of Alternation in order to guarantee the articulation of the University Time (TU) and Community Time (TC). Thus, the alternation as a curricular strategy allows systematizing the educational periods that are intensely interconnected - TU/TC. In this sense, Molina (2015) emphasizes that the courses also prepare educators beyond the classroom, so that they can act in school management processes and in community management processes. According to the Pedagogical Project of the Course (UFT, 2013), the University Time activities are carried out in the months of January/February and July/August, and during systematic meetings in the interval of each community constituent of the course subjects.

It is worth mentioning that the internship in licentiate degree differs from those of the Bachelor's degree, since it directs and prepares students to be educators in the future, that is, they constitute the foundation for the training of professionals of all categories (Bianchi, 2005). However, Barreiro (2006, p. 53) points out that "[...] many of the prepositions are far removed from the longings of organized movements and scientific entities, especially concerning to the formation of educators". In relation to the teacher training for Rural Education, this reality of detachment is more evident, since the laws that regulate the internship in the country do not even mention a thing about this type of teaching.

The origin of the teaching internship is linked to the institution of the supervised internship in Brazilian educational institutions, with the purpose of complementing the theoretical training of students, according to the Organic Law of Industrial Education, n°. 4,073 of 1942. It is worth noting that, despite the supervised internship has its origins in professional education, it is specified in the laws which govern it, that it is a social, professional and cultural learning which must be provided to the student for the participation in real life and work situations (Alves, Barbosa, & Dib, 2016, p. 74-75).

With this in mind, Andrade and Resende (2010) state that the Curricular Internship, which is understood as an educational act, requires trainees to work with the trainees, aspects related to planning, development, evaluation and results of the activities developed by them, of the whole organizational process of school work, since the trainees or future educators should, first of all, know the school context with regard to the pedagogical, administrative, financial and legal dimensions.

Therefore, it is believed that the teacher's pedagogical practice needs to be linked to theory and

practice and, in this regard, Pimenta (2009, p. 102) emphasizes, “[...] this training aims to prepare the trainee to carry out activities in the schools, with the teachers in the classrooms, as well as for the exercise of analysis, evaluation and criticism that makes possible the proposal of intervention projects based on the challenges and difficulties that the routine of the internship in schools reveals”.

In other areas, such as the arts, the positioning about the importance of the internship for the student formation agrees in the discussion proposed here: “I understand the Curricular Internship as a possibility for the university professor to research his/her practices based on the relationship with his/her students and with the knowledge, considering this as partial, in movement and process, and being constructed by the teacher with his trainee students” (Zamperetti, 2015, p. 24).

Similarly, in a study carried out in the area of biological sciences by Valladão (2014), the author draws attention to the fact that the student, during the internship, will realize that the school reality is very different from what he imagined. Facing this, it is important that the teachers of the university internship can enable these students to understand the importance of the internship in school, so that they can better understand the school reality, as well as the challenges and problems that exist in it. Thus, it is possible to perceive that the studies on supervised curricular internship in education are similar in an important point: they understand the relevance and necessity of the internship for the academic and intellectual formation of the student.

Specifically in the degree in Rural Education with a qualification in Arts and Music at the Federal University of Tocantins, Tocantinópolis campus, in Stage I, which takes place in the 5th period of the course, the total workload is 60 hours, of which 45 hours are devoted to theory - reading of texts in the classroom, orientation with teachers among others - and 15 hours focused on practice - internships in schools. At that moment, the student must carry out an observation phase of the school management, both in primary and secondary education. Unlike Stage I, the student in Stage II must complete an amount of 90 hours, being at this stage fully integrated into practice. Furthermore, at that moment, the stage of regency observation in the elementary school should be accomplished, besides a study directed through theoretical foundation, meetings with the teacher of the stage, and the Partial Report. However, in Stage III, the workload also increases: 120 hours dedicated to the practice, which should be accomplished in high school, from

the observation and regency. At this stage, the student should also conduct studies with a theoretical basis and meetings with the internship teacher, in addition to the Report. In the last stage, which occurs in the last period of the Rural Education course - 8th period - the students will have to carry out an intervention project in the school which will conduct the internship. Such intervention needs to be related to the arts area, in line with the pedagogical practices of rural education, which should correspond to a workload of 70 practical hours and 65 theoretical hours.

Material and methods

This case study is based on the qualitative research approach, which “[...] demands the world to be examined with the idea that nothing is trivial, that everything has the potential to constitute a clue which allows us to establish a more enlightening understanding of our object” (Bogdan & Biklen, 2010, p. 49). Moreover, it assumes an exploratory characteristic, which understands that it is necessary in order to increase the experience around the object of study (Triviños, 1987), since there is a lack of studies on this subject in rural education. Thus, it is important to delve into the reality studied, seeking to cast new questions, in search of production and advancement of knowledge for the area. In fact, this case study “[...] aims to deepen the description of a certain reality [...] to provide the in-depth knowledge of a delimited reality which the results achieved can allow and formulate hypotheses for the referral of other researches” (Triviños, 1987, p. 110).

In this methodological line, the method of interpretive research is aligned with the methodological tools used in this research - documentary and empirical analysis - and it is appropriate to the theoretical assumptions emphasized in this study.

According to Erickson (1985) the interpretive and qualitative work is characterized by a matter of substantial and intentional focus, since a research technique is not a research method. However, the narrative produced in the data collection can be used by researchers who are interested in knowing and revealing the meanings of the actions and behaviors of the ‘actors’ in the environment in which they are inserted and are researched.

For Erickson (1985), interpretive research is quite significant for education, since it is interested in the cultural and social space of the classroom and the teaching and learning process there, and in the meaning of the actions taken place in that same space, promoted by both the students and the

teacher during the educational process. For this theorist, the interpretive analysis must follow the specific and general description of the narrative, and must be carried out from the conducted observations, the interviews, the analyzed documents, among other methodological procedures used, in dialogue with the theoretical bases that ground the research and points of view of the researcher, then meeting the pretensions of this work.

There is no doubt that the field notes contain empirical statements that greatly aided the conclusions of this study. It should be pointed out that such statements can be produced by induction, that is, by researching and analyzing the field notes, and may even gauge the results found with other studies.

Interpretative research is concerned with the specificities of meaning and action in social life, which take place in concrete scenes of face-to-face interaction and in the wider society surrounding the scene of action. The conduct of interpretive research on teaching involves intense and ideally long-term participant observation in an educational setting, followed by de-liberate and long-term reflection on what was seen there. That reflection entails the observer's deliberate scrutiny of his/her own interpretive point of view and its sources in formal theory, culturally learned ways of seeing, and personal value commitments. As the participant observer learns more about the world out there, s/he also learns more about him/herself (Erickson, 1985, p. 131).

In agreement with the interpretative research, the semi-structured interview of 20 questions with the students of the last period of the degree in Rural Education was also used. The social contact with the interviewees was the first moment of the interview, in which the researchers were provided relevant data to this study, analyzed in the next topic. In this respect, it is important to emphasize that during the interviews, the interviewees were informed about the objectives of the research and its purposes, aiming to establish a cordial relationship between both (Szymanski, 2004). We interviewed 18 students from the last period, randomly chosen, in a universe of 55 students, who participated in all stages during the course at the Federal University of Tocantins, Tocantinópolis, Brazil, from 2016 to 2017.

In this sense, students' reports were collected throughout 2017 through tape audio recorders and later transcribed. The interviews took place in the Tocantinópolis campus, during non-school hours and with the voluntary participation of the students. Those who agreed to participate in the interviews

were presented the research objectives, as well as the methodology used, data collection form and the interview script to be carried out, prepared by the authors of this research.

Although interviewing as a data collection instrument cannot predominantly be guided by quantitative criteria, we understand that the greater the number of subjects interviewed, the more consistent the material about the analysis will be. However, considering the length of this article, 18 students were randomly chosen to interview in a universe of 55 students (enrolled in the course of internship 4), who participated in all the internships during the Rural Education course at the UFT, Tocantinópolis, from 2016 to 2017.

It is important to note that the interviewees' statements were organized as follows: interviewed A (2017); interviewed B (2017); interviewed C (2017); interviewed D (2017) and so on, with the aim of preserving their anonymity and attending to ethics in human sciences research. However, to analyze the interviews, we selected some significant portions of the speeches of these students to dialogue with authors who discuss the subject in question.

Another data collection instrument used in this research was the direct observation in the classroom during the internships held in the schools and in the internship course throughout the Rural Education course. In view of this, it is important to be theoretically based on observational research, since the theory related to the proposed study helped in the elaboration of reflections and analyzes of the data collected, producing scientific knowledge (Vianna, 2003).

The direct observation is used without manipulation or modification of the environment where the behaviors of the observed subjects occur, therefore, the participant research approach was not used, since it would not be adequate for this research. This type of observation is feasible when one wants to research a subject or group and the inquiries are directed and specific to both (Vianna, 2003). In addition to the interviews, different strategies were developed for data collection during the observation process: field notes of the internship classes and informal conversations with students and teachers who participated in the internships.

Findings

Thus, in this topic, we present the described and analyzed reports of the students of the degree in Rural Education with qualification in Arts and Music regarding the internship attended by them. It is important to note that not all students' answers

were selected, only the most significant, considering the dimensions of this article.

The internships in undergraduate courses, in general, are still worked very far from the reality of the Brazilian public schools (Pimenta, 2009). We believe that this distance in teacher training is a reflection of what is written in the legal documents that regulate the internship itself.

In this sense, the Supervised Curricular Internship goes far beyond a simple fulfillment of academic requirements, since it involves thinking about teaching-learning issues, as well as the specific issues of the environment where it occurs, because it is a social practice, considering also that it makes possible the practice allied to the theoretical knowledge in the life of undergraduate students, which still have in view an opportunity of personal and professional growth.

In the wake of these reflections, Pimenta (2009) points out that every profession is practical and technical. Practice in the sense of learning to do an activity, and the teacher's doing is also practical, because the students learn in some way with the teachers. It is technical because it uses methods and instruments for the developing activities. But it is worth mentioning that students, based on the practices of teachers, can elaborate methods that they consider the most appropriate for each school reality, under the supervision of a teacher/tutor of the internship.

When asked about what the Supervised Curricular Internship meant during the course, they answered:

Student A (2017):

The Supervised Curricular Internship meant a lot for me, because with this practice we can learn how the reality we will find when acting is, this practice helped me a lot with regard to shyness, at first I thought I would not be able to do it, but with room practice of class, I surpassed all my expectations, because in the internship process I established several bonds with the profession that I intend to follow.

Student B (2017):

It means that it is a step for a teacher in training to begin a practical work, to understand what their role is inside and outside the classroom, accompanied by a trained and experienced professional.

Student C (2017):

It means putting into practice a little of what you have learned during the course, presenting documents and a report your on internship to your advisor. The Supervised Internship prepares the individual to act in the classroom.

Student D (2017):

This is the internship we do during some periods to finish a graduation, giving a lesson to know the reality from within the classroom.

Student E (2017):

It means an internship where the teacher supervises throughout the process.

Student F (2017):

The supervised curricular internship for me is something that contributes to the formation of the academic student, however, in the case of rural education, except for internship IV, where we can choose how to work at the school, which type of project to develop, the internship ends up going against everything we have learned in theory and practice of the course itself. We have learned the pillars of a libertarian education, and are forced to internship within the dominant pattern. I believe that the rural education internships should take place in the EFAS (Agricultural Family Schools).

Student G (2017):

A practical opportunity in the role of being an educator.

Student H (2017):

For me, this period is an opportunity for us, as future educators, to put into practice all the knowledge that was acquired throughout our course in the graduation.

Student I (2017):

It is a way of taking practices to complement the formation of the graduate student in regard to pedagogical practices, because it is the moment in which the university students will experience and put into practice the theoretical knowledge that they have acquired in the university, improving their skills and knowledge in the classroom.

In their reports, it is possible to observe that the internship was significant in their lives, since the majority had an opportunity to put into practice the knowledge they learned and had contact during the graduation in Rural Education, specifically in the disciplines of Internship I, II, III and IV, in which they had contact with different theoretical texts on internship and teachers training. They also emphasize the importance of the internship as essential for training educators to work in the countryside. In this line of thought,

It is considered essential for current and future teachers to seek, based on studies and findings on the state of development of the teaching internship, to know the new educational and pedagogical practices, apply them and present them to postgraduate students, as well as the improvement in education, these changes also have repercussions on the professional, economic and social improvement of the country (Alves Barbosa, & Dib, 2016, p. 77).

Then the students were asked how their internship experience was in Art. Here are the answers:

Student C (2017):

The experience of practicing in the Art discipline was a unique experience, seeing that the different

languages addressed in the classroom, awakened in the student the need to deepen on these new approaches worked in the Art classes, these were unforgettable moments.

Student E (2017):

It was quite interesting, but at the same time it was complicated due to the fact of knowing the reality lived by the indigenous peoples, another complicated factor was the fact that they did not understand our language.

Student F (2017):

In my case it was wonderful, I had the opportunity to work with something that I love, although it is much more difficult nowadays, namely: The photograph. I worked with music too, however, I would feel much more willing to work with the visual arts.

Student G (2017):

This was an experience of great importance, however, when I studied I had two important experiences of acting in the two spheres: visual arts and music.

Student I (2017):

It was a very innovative experience, because before the course also had a vision as well as the students of that space, that the arts was only to paint and draw, and to be in that space as a teacher and with different ideas of them, about the concept of what arts are, it was a sense of ability to make the arts classes make it interesting.

The majority of the students interviewed made it clear in their speech that the internship in the Art course was a significant and challenging experience, as they also faced a cultural diversity of students (indigenous and peasants from different regions of the State, who were present in most of these classes). They also highlighted the difficulties present in the Art discipline, such as, for example, the non-valorization of this discipline in schools, when compared to the others in the school curriculum, which has a shorter workload compared to the other curricular subjects, as well as many teachers to teach this discipline without being trained in the area of art. Another challenge pointed out is that, generally, in the school context, this discipline is erroneously conceived only as drawing and painting, which makes clear the devaluation and lack of knowledge on the part of many students, teachers (not trained in this area) and school, in about this important area of knowledge.

In this line of thought, understanding “[...] the school as a professional institution of educators, with its organizational and structural characteristics and who are the educators, help us to understand the work of teachers and the possibilities of pedagogical practices that generate meaningful and

adequate learning to students” (Bitencourt & Zart, 2017, p. 257).

The training courses of rural educators, developed by universities, from the perspective of social movements, must be linked to a political project of social transformation, committed to the social function of producing knowledge as a possibility of human emancipation. The university faces the challenge of rethinking its pedagogical work, although it does not represent a complete paradigm shift (Gomes et al., 2017, p. 378).

In line with this reflection Zamperetti (2015) mentions that even though the arts are a fruitful field of the human creation and expression, it also needs to articulate theory and practice in this important moment for the university, because the student arrives to the school to train with many doubts, uncertainties, worries, and has a good preparation in this discipline in the university so that he can overcome these obstacles in the exercise of the teaching.

When asked about the meaning of being a teacher in the context of rural education, the students interviewed said the following:

Student A (2017):

It means having commitment and qualification and using a methodology that meets the needs of the students, not only within the educational unit, but also in their social environment, we should pass content that values the culture and the experience of the peasants.

Student C (2017):

It means a vast experience in acting as an educator, because they will be inside both a teaching learning with all the academic formality, but also, it will be inside social movements and the reality that an individual carries until arriving at the University.

Student E (2017):

It is knowing how to deal with the countryside reality and at the same time offering meaningful knowledge within the legal parameters imposed by society.

Student F (2017):

Being a teacher for this bias is knowing and recognizing oneself within the school space. It is knowing how to deal with the realities and cultural belongings of all the subjects inserted there. It is to be able to deal with the different situations, both of the reality of the school space and of the students.

Student H (2017):

Having a differentiated view of evaluating the student, knowing how to use his reality to teach and take into account the knowledge that he brings from home, and knowing that each student learns differently, and that we must seek new methodologies that reach all students.

Student I (2017):

For me, being a teacher in the context of Rural Education is not to exclude the peasantry from curricularly organized knowledge, but also to prepare them to understand and improve their living conditions in their cultural environment.

It is possible to verify in their reports that being a teacher in the countryside is to break with the hegemony that permeates the curriculum of Brazilian basic education schools, which are based on fragmented knowledge, usually considering the knowledge and skills coming from the countryside. Valladão (2014) corroborates this thought by stating that the teacher needs to be a knower of his practice, but also critical and questioning, so that he can be more active and participatory in his profession.

According to Gomes et al. (2017) the degree courses in Rural Education seek to overcome the traditional curricular model, which does not take into account the specificities and peasant reality. Hence, it is necessary to establish a practice of multidisciplinary teacher training, through the Pedagogy of Alternation.

Concerning the contributions of the internship to their formation as future educators in the countryside, the statements below given by the students attribute the importance of the internship to the teacher training is especially related with critical reflection by mentioning various aspects of the role of being an educator. Such assertions are indications that the Supervised Curricular Internship discipline has contributed to the training of future educators. This is perceived from the following considerations:

Student A (2017):

It helped me to understand how teachers work in the classroom and then see what works and what does not, and from then on, when acting in the classroom, not to make the same mistakes that they make in relation to the methodology, because it makes all the difference within the educational environment.

Student C (2017):

It brought a certain security and firmness at the time of the practical internship, because we had a good preparation for this in the matter of dealing with the presence of black people, riverines, quilombola community, militants, among others.

Student D (2017):

It gave me the understanding to value the students' individual knowledge and a different view of what it is to be a teacher trained in the art discipline.

Student F (2017):

Knowledge and in fact the understanding of true reality of both the school and the classroom and the methods to be approached in regard to the future educator of the country school.

Student H (2017):

The internship gives me a preview of how the classroom environment is and what difficulties I will face in the future, and learning in practice makes all the difference to a good training.

Student I (2017):

I would say that the internship provided the practice of what was theoretically learned in the course, because it led me to look at the student as a historical being who deserves to be looked at in his singularity as an individual rather than mass.

In this sense, Alves et al. (2016) point out that it is necessary and important that the teacher and the student have an easy dialogue, so that they can solve the problems that may appear during the teacher training, autonomously and problematizing. And this, according to theorists, is possible through the practice of the teaching stage.

By analyzing the considerations listed in the interviewees about the suggestions for better completion of the internship in schools, there are really many aspects to be rethought. That is why the authors Silva and Lima (2016, p. 33) point out that:

[...] the supervised internship discipline should be regarded as one of the most significant, space where the theory acquired is put into practice and the work environment of the teacher is experienced for many for the first time, bringing in itself a series of questions, doubts and even insecurities. With this, depending on the way the discipline is developed, it can no longer contribute to enriching knowledge and becoming mere requirement to complete the degree.

In view of the statements of the interviewees in this research, it is possible to see the importance of the internship for the training of educators in the countryside. However, they are also emphasized by some of the challenges for the internship, ranging from the bureaucratic part of the documentation to the specific issues of the course itself, such as adapting to the Pedagogy of Alternation, the accompaniment of teachers during the internships in schools and a better dialogue between the university and the schools. However, it is important to emphasize that the university professor must know how to articulate both the knowledge on the specific area and the skills related to the problematization of this knowledge with the students (Alves et al., 2016).

It is possible to identify in their reports that the practice in school was an exciting and challenging experience, because the students could, in loco, know a little more of the teaching practice and put into practice the knowledge acquired in the internship of the Rural Education course.

Conclusion

The analysis of the empirical and theoretical data of this work was performed through the technique of the interpretative research. In this perspective, the study carried out showed that the Supervised Curricular Internship in the degree in Rural Education is a discipline that allows the construction of different knowledge and that this provides future educators to fight for an education in the countryside that can not only bring knowledge to subjects, but foster the production of knowledge inherent to their ways of living and producing in the countryside, involving social, political, cultural and economic aspects.

The theoretical posture brought in this article, as well as the reflections produced, are important to understand how the internship can contribute to the educator formation for the countryside, since studies on this subject in the Brazilian scientific literature are still incipient, which reinforces the relevance of this research to the knowledge area .

The degree in Rural Education with a qualification in Arts and Music at the Federal University of Tocantins emerged from the struggles of social movements to meet the rural population. Given this, it is necessary to train professionals to respond to the specificities of the countryside and meet the demand for basic education in the State.

Therefore, in order to overcome the challenges faced in the course, it demands the elaboration of a joint training proposal between the training institutions and the school, in order to guarantee actions that will attend the diverse subjects, especially those from the Rural Education.

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